

Effect of anionic surfactant on the protonation equilibria of L-phenylalanine and maleic acid

Malla Ramanaiah^{a,b}, V. Gowri Kumari^b and B. B. V. Sailaja^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Aditya Institute of Technology and Management, Tekkali-532 201, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Inorganic & Analytical Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : sailaja_bbv@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received online 25 June 2015, accepted 25 August 2015

Abstract : The impact of sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) on the protonation equilibria of L-phenylalanine (Phe) and maleic acid (MA) has been studied in various concentrations (0.0–2.5% w/v) of sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) solution maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ at 303 K. The protonation constants have been calculated with the computer program MINIQUAD75 and the best fit models are arrived at based on statistical grounds employing crystallographic *R* factor, χ^2 , skewness and kurtosis. These protonation constants values have been found to shift in micellar media as compared to those in pure water. The differences in the values have been attributed to the solvent properties of the interfacial and bulk phases involving contribution from the micellar surface potential in the case of charged micelles. The trend of log values of step-wise protonation constants with mole fraction of the medium have been explained based on electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces operating on the protonation equilibria. Distributions of species, protonation equilibria and effect of influential parameters on the protonation constants have also been presented.

Keywords : Protonation equilibria, MINIQUAD75, sodium lauryl sulphate, L-phenylalanine, maleic acid.

Introduction

A number of studies have been reported on protonation constants of α -amino acids in different media^{1–3}. Acidity and basicity of a molecule is governed by its structure and solvent effects^{4,5}. L-Phenylalanine (Phe) is an electrically neutral amino acid. It is one of the twenty common amino acids used to biochemically form proteins, coded for by DNA. Phe is biologically converted into L-tyrosine. L-Tyrosine in turn is converted into L-DOPA, which is further converted into dopamine, norepinephrine and epinephrine. Phenylalanine is converted to cinnamic acid by the enzyme phenylalanine ammonia-lyase⁶. L-Phenylalanine produced commercially has been increased by genetically engineering *E. coli*, such as by altering the regulatory promoters or amplifying the number of genes controlling enzymes responsible for the synthesis of the amino acid⁷.

Maleic acid (MA) is a dicarboxylic acid, maleic is mainly used as a precursor to fumaric acid, and relative

to its parent maleic anhydride, maleic acid has few applications. In industry, maleic acid is derived by hydrolysis of maleic anhydride, the later being produced by oxidation of benzene or butane. Maleic acid is an industrial raw material for the production of glyoxylic acid by ozonolysis. The major industrial use of maleic acid is its conversion to fumaric acid. Maleic acid does not spontaneously interconvert into fumaric acid because rotation around a carbon carbon double bond is energetically not favorable.

Sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) or sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) is an anionic surfactant and profoundly influences the bulk properties of physiological systems. They can solubilise, concentrate and compartmentalize ions and molecules⁸. Hence, the influence of anionic micellar media on the protonation equilibria of Phe and MA are investigated in the presence of SLS. The use of aqueous micellar media is wide and varied such as in pharmaceuticals, analytical chemistry, organic synthesis and several industrial applications. Amphiphilic molecules, contain-

ing both hydrophobic and hydrophilic moieties, associate in water above a certain concentration to form colloidal particles called micelles⁹. Micellar systems can shift acid-base equilibria. This shift in chemical equilibria can be explained in terms of differences between the properties of the bulk solvent and of the interfacial region and perturbation of the acid-base equilibria by the electrostatic field effect of the charged interface¹⁰. The dissociation equilibria of substituted benzoic acids in cationic and anionic micelles have been investigated potentiometrically¹¹. It was shown that their pK_a values shift to about 0.5–3.0 in anionic micelles. The acid-base equilibria of a number of phenols, amines and carboxylic acids in aqueous micellar solutions have been examined¹². The present work is an attempt to study the effects of anionic micellar solution on the protonation equilibria of the two biologically or industrially useful acids, viz. Phe and MA in the surfactant SLS.

Experimental

Materials :

Solutions (0.05 mol L⁻¹) of L-phenylalanine (Loba, India) and maleic acid (Loba, India) were prepared in triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid concentration to increase the solubility. Sodium lauryl sulphate (Merck, India) was used as received. Nitric acid (Merck, India) of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. Sodium nitrate (Merck, India) of 2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) of 0.4 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess errors in concentration determinations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification¹³. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{14,15}.

Instrumentation and analytical procedures :

Alkalimetric titrations were carried out in media containing varying compositions of sodium lauryl sulfate (0.0–2.5% w/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium nitrate at 303 ± 0.05 K an Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. Potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 mol L⁻¹) and borax (0.01 mol L⁻¹) solutions were used to calibrate the pH meter. In each titration, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol of nitric acid. The amounts of the ligands in the titrands ranged between 0.25 and

0.50 mmol. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred sodium lauryl sulfate-water mixture containing inert electrolyte for several days. At regular intervals titration of strong acid against alkali to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. The calomel electrode was refilled with SLS-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. The initial concentrations of reactants are given in Table 1. The details of experimental procedure and titration assembly have been detailed elsewhere^{16–18}.

Table 1. Total initial concentrations of reactants (in mmol) in proton-ligand titrations

% w/v	No. of titration curves	TLO	
		Phe	MA
0.0	3	0.2494	0.2498
		0.3741	0.3747
		0.4988	0.4996
0.5	3	0.2503	0.2503
		0.3754	0.3754
		0.5006	0.5006
1.0	3	0.2489	0.2494
		0.3733	0.3741
		0.4878	0.4988
1.5	3	0.2478	0.2484
		0.3717	0.3726
		0.4956	0.4968
2.0	3	0.2478	0.2484
		0.3717	0.3726
		0.4956	0.4968
2.5	3	0.2494	0.2489
		0.3741	0.3733
		0.4988	0.4878

Modeling strategy :

The approximate protonation constants of Phe and MA were calculated with the computer program SCPHD^{19–21}. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program, MINQUAD7522, which exploit the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. The variation of stepwise protonation constants (log K) with the mole fraction of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds for the solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

Secondary formation functions :

Secondary formation functions like average number of protons bound per mole of ligand (\bar{n}_H) and number of moles of alkali consumed per mole of ligand (\mathbf{a}) are useful to detect the number of equilibria. Plots of \bar{n}_H versus pH for different concentrations of the ligand should overlap if there is no formation of polymeric species. Overlapping formation curves for Phe and MA (Fig. 1) rule out the polymerization of the ligand molecules. The pH values at half integral values of \bar{n}_H correspond to the protonation constants of the ligands. Two half integrals (1.5 and 0.5) in the case of Phe (Fig. 1A) and MA (Fig. 1B) emphasize the presence of two protonation-deprotonation equilibria in the pH range of present study. The number of plateaus in the formation curves corresponds to the number of these equilibria.

Fig. 1. Plots of \bar{n}_H versus pH in 2.5% w/v SLS-water mixture : (A) Phe, (B) MA; (Δ) 0.25, (\circ) 0.375 and (\square) 0.50 mmol, respectively.

The plots of \mathbf{a} versus pH are given in Fig. 2. The negative values of \mathbf{a} correspond to the number of moles of free acid present in the titrand and the number of associable protons. The positive values of \mathbf{a} indicate the number of dissociable protons in the ligand molecules. The maximum value of \mathbf{a} in Fig. 2(A) is +1, which indicates that Phe has one dissociable (one carboxyl) proton. The corresponding value for MA in Fig. 2(B) is +2, which clearly infers that maleic acid has two dissociable (two carboxyl) protons.

Fig. 2. Variation of \mathbf{a} with pH in 2.0% w/v SLS-water mixture : (A) Phe and (B) MA, respectively.

Distribution diagrams :

Typical distribution plots produced by DISPLOT²³⁻²⁶ using protonation constants from the best fit models are shown in Fig. 3. A single representative plot is shown for each system at a particular SLS-water concentration. The zwitterion of Phe, LH, is present to an extent of 97% in the pH range 1.6–10.0. The distribution plot of Phe in Fig. 3(A) shows the existence of LH_2^+ , L^- . In the case

Fig. 3. Formation functions (•) and species distribution diagrams of (A) Phe and (B) MA in 0.5% w/v SLS-water mixtures.

of MA, LH^- is present to an extent of 95% in the pH range 1.5–10.0. The distribution plots of MA in Fig. 3(B) show the existence of LH_2 , L^{2-} . The corresponding protonation-deprotonation equilibria are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of (A) Phe and (B) MA.

Residual analysis :

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on the model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian or normal distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should be ideally equal to zero. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis of the least squares analysis, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , skewness, kurtosis and *R*-factor. These statistical parameters of the present data show that the best fit models portray the acido-basic equilibria of Phe and MA in SLS-water mixtures, as discussed below. Alkali metric titration data are simulated using the model parameters given in Table 2.

χ^2 test :

χ^2 is a special case of gamma distribution whose probability density function is an asymmetrical function. This distribution measures the probability of residuals forming a part of standard normal distribution with zero mean and unit standard deviation. If the χ^2 calculated is less than the table value, the model is accepted.

Crystallographic R-test :

Hamilton's *R* factor ratio test is applied in complex equilibria to decide whether inclusion of more species in the model is necessary or not. In pH-metric method the readability of pH meter is taken as the R_{limit} , which represents the upper boundary of *R* beyond which the model bears no significance. When these are different numbers of species the models whose values are greater than *R*-table are rejected. The low crystallographic *R*-values given in Table 2 indicate the sufficiency of the model.

Skewness :

It is a dimensionless quantity indicating the shape of the error distribution profile. A value of zero for skewness indicates that the underlying distribution is symmetrical. If the skewness is greater than zero, the peak of the error distribution curve is to the left of the mean and the peak is to the right of the mean if skewness is less than zero. The values of skewness recorded in Table 2 are between -1.10 and 0.81. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data.

Table 2. Best fit chemical models of acido-basic equilibria of Phe and MA in SLS-water mixtures
Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹

% w/v SLS	log β ₁ (SD)	log β ₂ (SD)	NP	U _{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ ²	R-factor
L-Phenylalanine (pH ranges 1.8–10.30)								
0	9.27(1)	11.48(1)	72	1.85	-0.17	3.27	1.22	0.0096
0.5	8.94(1)	11.59(4)	39	10.54	0.13	2.30	5.49	0.0285
1.0	8.36(2)	11.27(4)	54	18.65	0.81	4.60	7.56	0.0342
1.5	8.73(2)	12.02(4)	36	12.05	-0.06	3.57	15.11	0.0137
2.0	8.85(2)	12.37(4)	54	15.57	0.28	2.54	3.85	0.0246
2.5	9.15(1)	12.80(3)	67	13.07	0.04	4.70	20.87	0.0146
Maleic acid (pH ranges 1.5–10.00)								
0	6.15(1)	7.93(2)	102	6.80	-0.29	4.94	7.45	0.0151
0.5	5.75(2)	7.50(2)	28	14.21	-1.10	3.98	9.71	0.0347
1.0	5.58(1)	7.28(2)	30	27.14	-0.22	3.32	6.93	0.0097
1.5	5.73(3)	6.99(5)	40	3.15	-1.25	6.40	19.00	0.0227
2.0	5.52(1)	6.79(2)	47	7.11	-0.09	7.66	16.47	0.0087
2.5	5.81(1)	7.75(2)	63	10.16	-0.32	4.27	4.16	0.0145

U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) × 10⁸; NP = Number of points; m = number of protonation constants; SD = standard deviation.

Kurtosis :

It is a measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a model value. For an ideal normal distribution kurtosis value should be three (mesokurtic). If the calculated kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form mesokurtic pattern in the case of Phe and leptokurtic for MA. Alkalimetric titration data are simulated using the model parameters given in Table 2. These data are compared with the experimental alkalimetric titration data, to verify the sufficiency of the models. The overlap of the typical experimental and simulated titrations data given in Fig. 5 indicates that the proposed models represent the experimental data.

Effect of surfactant :

The interface of anionic surfactant SDS is negatively charged and the anion from the acid molecule is repelled, thus leading to a decrease in acidity. Also, there is a possibility of electrostatic attraction of H⁺ from acid molecule to the SDS micelles, which would cause an increase in the acidity. However, in the present study, the sum total of these factors cause lesser strain on the acid molecule leading to small variation of stepwise protonation constant values as compared to those in water. The pri-

Fig. 5. Simulated (o) and experimental (solid line) alkalimetric titration curves in 0.5% w/v SLS-water mixtures : (A) Phe and (B) MA acid; (a) 0.25, (b) 0.375 and (c) 0.50 mmol, respectively.

primary factor in the micellar effect on lower alkyl amines^{28,29} is the electrostatic interaction of the amine cation and anionic surface of SLS micelle while the hydrophobic interaction plays only a secondary role. Similar situation prevails for Phe under the present experimental conditions. The protonation equilibria of these ligands have significant influence on their metabolism. Anions of SLS bind to the main peptide chain at a ratio of one SLS anion for every two amino acid residues. This effectively imparts a negative charge on the protein that is proportional to the mass of that protein (about 1.4 g SLS/g protein).

The apparent variation in the magnitude of protonation constants in micellar media compared to aqueous solution (Fig. 6) was attributed to the creation of concentration gradient of protons between the interface and the bulk solution³⁰. Further the presence of micelles is known

to alter the dielectric constant of the medium, which has direct influence on the protonation-deprotonation equilibria^{31,32}. The almost linear variation of log values of stepwise protonation constants with the mole fraction of L-phenylalanine in SLS-water mixtures indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria. Some non-linearity in case of maleic acid due the contributions from non-electrostatic or hydrophobic interactions between the solute and the solvent.

Protonation constants of Phe and MA in CTAB-water mixture and TX100-water mixture have already reported in my earlier reports^{33,18}. The effect of anionic, cationic and neutral micellar media on stepwise protonation constants of Phe and MA has shown in Fig. 7. The log values of stepwise protonation constants of L-phenylalanine more

Fig. 6. Variation of stepwise protonation constant ($\log K$) with mole fraction of SLS in SLS-water mixtures : (A) Phe and (B) MA; (■) $\log K_1$, (●) $\log K_2$.

Fig. 7. Variation of stepwise protonation constant ($\log K$) with mole fraction of micelle in micelles-water mixtures : (A) Phe : SLS (■) $\log K_1$, (●) $\log K_2$; CTB : (▲) $\log K_1$, (▼) $\log K_2$; TX100 : (◄) $\log K_1$, (►) $\log K_2$; (B) MA : SLS (■) $\log K_1$, (●) $\log K_2$; CTB : (▲) $\log K_1$, (▼) $\log K_2$; TX100 : (◄) $\log K_1$, (►) $\log K_2$.

varied in TX100-water mixture and increase of maleic acid greatly influenced in CTAB-water mixture. The log values of protonation constants of Phe and MA increased almost linearly with increasing mole fraction of TX100-water mixtures indicating the dominance of electrostatic forces in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria and hydrogen bonding in TX100. The linear variation of log values of protonation constants of L-phenylalanine with increasing mole fraction of CTAB-water mixtures indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria. MA exhibits a non-linear trend indicating the dominance of non-electrostatic forces/hydrophobic interactions between the solute and the solvent. The stoichiometric protonation constants of L-phenylalanine and maleic acid determined in various micelles-water mixtures were listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Stoichiometric protonation constants of Phe and MA in micelles-water mixtures
Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

% w/v	L-Phenylalanine					
	SLS		CTAB		TX100	
Micelles	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
0.0	2.21	9.27	2.21	9.27	2.21	9.27
0.5	2.65	8.94	3.28	8.8	2.46	9.47
1.0	2.91	8.36	3.11	8.75	3.45	8.68
1.5	3.29	8.73	2.95	8.64	2.43	9.26
2.0	3.52	8.85	3.47	8.71	2.86	9.69
2.5	3.65	9.15	4.19	8.66	2.74	9.56
Maleic acid						
0.0	1.78	6.15	1.78	6.15	1.78	6.15
0.5	1.75	5.75	3.34	6.73	1.96	5.95
1.0	1.7	5.58	3.79	6.48	2.22	6.08
1.5	1.26	5.73	3.55	6.36	2.12	6.19
2.0	1.27	5.52	3.52	6.13	2.71	6.22
2.5	1.94	5.81	3.52	6.13	2.61	6.25

Effect of systematic errors in best fit model :

MINIQUAD75 does not have provision to study the effect of systematic errors in the influential parameters like the concentration of reactants and electrode calibration on the magnitude of protonation constant. In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the concen-

tration of alkali, mineral acids and the ligands. The results of a typical system given in Table 4 emphasize that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and mineral acid affects the protonation constants more than that of the ligand.

Table 4. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the protonation constants of Phe and MA in 2.5% (w/v) SLS-water mixture

Reactants	% Error	Phe		MA	
		log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)
Acid	0	9.15(1)	12.80(3)	5.81(1)	7.75(2)
	-5	8.81(2)	11.99(4)	5.44(2)	7.03(4)
	-2	9.02(1)	12.49(3)	5.67(1)	7.47(2)
	+2	9.29(2)	13.13(5)	5.96(2)	8.04(3)
	+5	9.50(4)	13.64(10)	5.96(2)	8.04(3)
Alkali	-5	9.57(4)	13.62(8)	6.41(7)	8.71(8)
	-2	9.32(2)	13.12(5)	6.03(3)	8.11(4)
	+2	8.99(1)	12.51(3)	5.60(1)	7.42(2)
	+5	8.76(2)	12.07(4)	5.29(4)	6.91(6)
Ligand	-5	9.10(2)	12.84(4)	5.64(2)	7.52(2)
	-2	9.13(1)	12.82(3)	5.74(1)	7.66(2)
	+2	9.17(1)	12.79(3)	5.88(2)	7.84(2)
	+5	9.20(1)	12.78(3)	5.97(2)	7.97(3)
	Volume	-5	9.15(2)	12.83(4)	5.81(1)
log F	-2	9.15(1)	12.81(3)	5.80(1)	7.78(2)
	+2	9.15(1)	12.80(3)	5.81(1)	7.71(2)
	+5	9.15(2)	12.78(4)	5.80(1)	7.65(2)
	-5	9.13(1)	12.75(3)	5.79(1)	7.63(2)
	-2	9.14(1)	12.78(3)	5.80(1)	7.71(2)
+2	9.16(1)	12.83(3)	5.82(1)	7.80(2)	
+5	9.17(1)	12.86(3)	5.83(1)	7.86(2)	

Conclusions

- (i) L-Phenylalanine has one dissociable proton and one amino group which can associate with a proton. It exists as LH_2^+ at low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH and L^- successively with increase in pH.
- (ii) Maleic acid has two dissociable protons. It exists as LH_2 at low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH^- and L^{2-} successively with increase in pH.
- (iii) Secondary formation functions-number of moles of alkali consumes per mole of the ligand and average number of moles of protons bound per

mole of the ligand – are useful in detecting the number of protonation equilibria and in guessing the approximate protonation constants.

- (iv) The linear variation of log values of stepwise protonation constants with the mole fraction of L-phenylalanine in SLS-water mixtures indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria. The non-linear part in case of maleic acid due the contributions from non-electrostatic or hydrophobic interactions between the solute and the solvent.
- (v) The effect of systematic errors in the influential parameters shows that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and mineral acids will affect the protonation constants more than that of the ligand, volume of acid and log F .

References

1. P. S. Rao, B. Srikanth, V. S. Rao, C. Kamala Sastry and G. N. Rao, *E-J. Chem.*, 2009, **6**, 561.
2. M. P. Latha, V. M. Rao, T. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2007, **54**, 160.
3. M. S. Babu, G. N. Rao, K. V. Ramana and M. S. P. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 380.
4. R. W. Taf, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **14**, 247.
5. H. S. Harned and C. M. Birdsall, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 54.
6. S. Yamada, K. Nabe, N. Izuo, K. Nakamichi and I. Chibata, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 1981, **42**, 773.
7. M. B. Rao, A. M. Tanksale, M. S. Ghatge and V. V. Deshpande, *Microbiol. Mol. Biol. Rev.*, 1998, **62**, 597.
8. E. Pelizzetti and E. Pramaro, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **169**, 1.
9. M. Szymula and S. Radzki, *Colloid Surf. (B)*, 2004, **35**, 249.
10. P. V. Jaiswal V. S. Ijeri and A. K. Srivastava, *Colloid Surf. (B)*, 2005, **46**, 45.
11. P. Ezzio and P. Edmondo, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **117**, 403.
12. C. J. Drummond, F. Grieser and T. W. Healy, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1989, **85**, 521.
13. R. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, "Computer Applications in Chemistry", Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, 2005, 302.
14. G. Gran, *The Analyst*, 1952, **77**, 661.
15. G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **206**, 111.
16. M. Ramanaiah, S. Goutham sri and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Chem. Speciat. Bioavail.*, 2013, **25**, 285.
17. M. Ramanaiah, S. Goutham sri and B. B. V. Sailaja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **91**, 351.
18. M. Ramanaiah and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Chem. Speciat. Bioavail.*, 2014, **26**, 119.
19. M. Ramanaiah and B. B. V. Sailaja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **91**, 639.
20. M. Ramanaiah, P. Seetharam and B. B. V. Sailaja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **91**, 1011.
21. M. Ramanaiah, S. Goutham sri and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiopia*, 2014, **28**, 383.
22. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.
23. M. Ramanaiah, Ch. Nageswara Rao and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Proc. National Acad. Sci. India*, 2014, **84**, 485.
24. M. Ramanaiah and B. B. V. Sailaja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **91**, 1649.
25. M. Ramanaiah, S. Goutham sri and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Chem. Speciat. Bioavail.*, 2014, **26**, 231.
26. Ch. Nageswara Rao, M. Ramanaiah and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Chem. Speciat. Bioavail.*, 2014, **26**, 266.
27. R. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, "Computer Applications in Chemistry", Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, 2005, 277.
28. S. Harada, H. Okada, T. Sano, T. Yamashita and H. Yano, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 7648.
29. S. Harada, T. Doi, T. Sano, T. Yamashita and H. Yano, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1990, **63**, 2698.
30. G. S. Hartly and J. W. Roe, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 101.
31. C. A. Bunton, *Catal. Rev. Sci. Enz.*, 1979, **20**, 1.
32. H. Chaimovich, M. J. Politi, J. B. S Bonilha and F. H. Quina, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1979, **83**, 1851.
33. M. Ramanaiah and B. B. V. Sailaja, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 2014, **3**, 1118.